

Maxwell-Boltzmann $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ Condition and Maximum Entropy

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We suggest that the condition $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ ((1)) is the underlying idea of the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach and follows from a reaction balance type of picture. We suggest, however, that there is another physical way in which to interpret this result, namely that it means that removing energy e_i+e_j from a system has the same probability regardless of how the energy is removed i.e. whether one removes one particle with energy E or n particles whose energy sums to E .

The question arises: How does such a definition link with the idea of maximization of entropy subject to the average energy constraint (which is a special constraint)? A second question is: Is this entropy physical or simply a mathematical function?

We suggest that ((1)) may be applied to any number of particles i.e. even $N \rightarrow \infty$ = the number of particles in the system. In such a case $n(e_i)=Np(e_i)$. Then the energy on the RHS of ((1)) is $\sum_i p(e_i)e_i$. Using ((1)) leads to: $\exp\{\prod_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))\} = \exp(\text{constant}^2 * E_{ave}) = \exp(\sum_i p(e_i)e_i)$. A solution is: $\ln(p(e_i)) = e_i \cdot \text{constant}$ where $\text{constant} = -1/T$. (The same result follows directly from $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$).

$\prod_i p(e_i)$ (power $p(e_i)^N$) represents all particles in the system i.e. it is a probability of the N particle system. Conceptually, one might consider an ensemble of such systems and remove each particle one at a time from each system. Removing particles one at a time leads to different permutations of the particles removed in time. The product of $p(e_i)$'s for each system in the ensemble is the same. Thus there are two probabilities. One is the system probability $\prod_i p(e_i)$ (power $Np(e_i)$) and the second is $1/\text{number of permutations of the set of } Np(e_i)\text{'s}$. In general these two probabilities could be different even though $E_{ave} \text{ particle} = \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total}/N$. It is condition (1) which leads to $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ which makes $1/\text{number of permutations}$ the same value as the system product of $p(e_i)$ (power $Np(e_i)$) if one maximizes the number of permutations subject to the energy constraint. In other words, what would normally be two pieces of information, system product probability and $1/\text{permutation}$, become one and the same.

We suggest that the approach of removing one particle at a time from a system is equivalent to a single particle being in different e_i states at different times. Thus maximum entropy suggests maximum number of arrangements in time of the single particle energy and thus has physical meaning. In other words, the maximization of a certain math function $p(e_i)\ln(p(e_i))$ subject to a special constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ is not simply a math procedure.

Maxwell-Boltzmann $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ Condition

The condition $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ ((1)), which may be generalized to any number of products of probabilities, seems to be directly linked to a time reversal reaction balance. In other words, the probability for e_i , e_j and e_k to combine is assumed to be proportional to the product of them being together at the same place at the same time which is proportional to $p(e_i)p(e_j)p(e_k)$. In such a case, three particles disappear and become one with energy $e_i+e_j+e_k$, but if at the same time one particle with energy $e_i+e_j+e_k$ (which has a probability of $p(e_i+e_j+e_k)$ of being found)

breaks into three particles with energy e_i, e_j and e_k , the system will be in equilibrium. It is thus energy and probability which are conserved.

Another physical way in which to envisage this condition is to consider removing particles one at a time from a system. The probability of removing a particle with energy $e_i + e_j$ is the same as the product of $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ i.e. the probability of removing an e_i and an e_j . This may be generalized to removing any number of particles.

Generalization to Removing All N Particles of the System

If one considers generalizing ((1)) to the situation in which one removes all N particles in the system (for $N \rightarrow$ infinite), there should be $Np(e_i)$ particles with energy e_i etc. This means that the total energy on the RHS of ((1)) is:

$$E_{\text{total}} = \sum_i n(e_i) e_i \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{or} \quad E_{\text{total}}/N = E_{\text{ave particle}} = \sum_i e_i p(e_i) \quad ((2b))$$

((1)) becomes for the case of N particles being removed:

$$\text{Product over } i \text{ } p(e_i)^{Np(e_i)} = p(E_{\text{total}}) \quad ((3))$$

Writing the LHS side of ((3)) in terms of \ln yields: $\exp\{\sum_i Np(e_i)\ln(p(e_i))\} = p(E_{\text{total}})$ ((4))

This suggests that a solution is: $\ln(p(e_i)) = e_i * \text{constant}$ ((5))

((5)) is the Maxwell-Boltzmann result which follows just as readily from the \ln of $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ being compared with $e_i+e_j = (e_i+e_j)$.

((3)) shows that the system product probability is a constant. The question is how is ((3)) related to the maximization of entropy subject to the special constraint of $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave particle}}$? One may note that if one has an ensemble of systems, one may remove the particles of each system in different ways, but each is a permutation of the other. The number of permutations is:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)! \quad \text{Where } n(e_i) = Np(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

Thus there are two probabilities:

- (A) The system product of probabilities ((3))
- (B) $1/$ number of permutations where number of permutations = number of systems in the ensemble

Formally, the result ((5)) is equivalent to maximizing the \ln of the number of permutations subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave particle}}$ i.e. minimizing the probability.

This we argue seems to suggest maximizing the arrangements in a time sequence i.e. a system in the ensemble represents pulling out each particle one at a time. This should be equivalent to the set of energy values a single particle may have at successive instants in time.

As a result, it seems that one does not need any notion of entropy or its maximization subject to the special constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ to obtain $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((5)). There, however, seems to be an interpretation of this result in terms of a maximum number of arrangements in time i.e a single particle may take on a maximum number of arrangements in time if the proper $p(e_i)$ is chosen. In this sense it seems that entropy is a physical concept microscopically.

Conclusion

The Maxwell-Boltzmann condition seems to be based on the idea $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ ((1)) which is a reaction balance type of argument. This leads immediately to the MB distribution with no maximization of entropy subject to the special constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. One may ask: Why does one need entropy? What physical picture does it introduce?

We suggest that ((1)) may be interpreted as suggesting that the probability of pulling a particle with energy e_i+e_j out of a system is the same as the product of probabilities of pulling out an e_i and an e_j . This suggests the notion of an ensemble of systems with each system having its particles pulled out one at a time. This leads to a total number of systems in the ensemble of: $N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!$. Physically we argue that each system with its particle pulled out one at a time is equivalent to the different energy states a single particle may be in at successive times.

The result $\ln(p(e_i))=-e_i/T$ follows from ((1)) with no maximization of entropy, but is equivalent to a maximization of the entropy i.e. \ln of the number of permutations subject to the special constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. This follows formally from math. We suggest that the physical reason for considering this maximization as being more than a math process is that it represents a description of a single particle changing its energy values in time. Thus one wishes to minimize the probability of permutations of $n(e_i)$ values in time. This minimum probability (1/permutations) which is equivalent to a maximum entropy or maximum number of permutations suggests a maximum randomness in e_i values in time subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$.